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Impact of Quality Assurance on performance of projects in selected faith - based organizations in Uganda, a case study of Caritas Nebbi

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Abstract

This study explored the impact of quality assurance on performance of faith – based organizations, with Caritas Nebbi in Uganda as a case study. Precisely, the study scrutinized the impact of inspections, project goals, audits, and risk management on project performance. A descriptive research design was utilized, and data was gathered from 181 respondents selected from 310 using Yamane’s formula and stratified sampling techniques respectively. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires, while secondary data were collected from organizational documents. Data analysis was conducted using descriptive statistics, Pearson's correlation and multiple regression analysis with SPSS. The outcomes revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between quality assurance practices and project performance in Caritas Nebbi. The findings of the objectives indicated that a positive significance on project performance of Caritas Nebbi. This implied that regular inspections had contributed to improved compliance with standards, early detection of defects and timely corrective measures which mutually improved project performance in terms of quality and efficiency in Caritas Nebbi. Assessing the effects of achieved project goals as planned reveal optimistic and significant correlation between achieving goals as planned on project performance suggested that Caritas Nebbi adhered to planned timelines, budgets and outputs which registered improved performance. In determining the effect of audits on project performance of Caritas Nebbi, the analysis showed a weak insignificance between audits and project performance in Caritas Nebbi. The implication was that while audits

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were important for accountability and compliance, they might not have directly translated into enhanced performance unless their findings were effectively implemented and conducted simply as procedural requirements limiting impact on improved project performance of Caritas Nebbi. Risk management showed that proactive identification, assessment and mitigation of risks significantly improved project performance in Caritas Nebbi. Risk management and audit exhibited strong influence on project performance, while inspections and project goals showed significant impact. The study concluded that effective quality assurance practices significantly enhance project performance in faith – based organizations and recommends strengthening quality assurance systems to improve project outcomes.

1.0 Introduction

Quality assurance refers to a discipline and a job that is focused on offering confidence and guaranteeing that a project will meet all quality aspects and requirements (Eder, 20214). Quality assurance focuses on ensuring that a project or product meets both internal and external quality expectations. Internally, quality assurance ensures that a project meets organizational needs.

Sahil & Samiksha (2020) opine that quality assurance are becoming more and more important factors to project managers which enhances the project's standard and uniformity. And further elaborate on quality assurance being adoptive to proactive processes aiming at precluding problems.

Heldman, (2009) opines that quality constraints are restricted by the specifications of the product or service and also the expected standards required. Resource constraint deals with availability of resources (both internally to the project team and externally to other supports required for project execution) for project execution in terms of required skills, quantity, and experience and so on. Superior quality of the project management improves organizational performance excellence, but their collective leverage is often misused. Project performance may be improved by using quality practices. Leaders who grasp project quality management will be more successful on individual projects as well as on a portfolio of investments for their businesses. (Kloppenborg & Petrick, 2002).

Quality assurance is applied throughout the project processes to ensure the successful completion of projects. Thus, it is suitable for all kinds of projects irrespective of their types, design, activity, or industry. The importance of quality assurance cannot be neglected as “It is not possible to produce a desired quality and maintain it consistently over a length of period unless adequate control is exercised at every stage” (Jain 2001). Therefore, contrary to general perception, quality assurance is not just limited to control of measurements, tolerances, and quality indicators. Somewhat it is combined into all the phases and processes implemented in the project.

1.2 Statement of the problem

Quality assurance involves adhering to standards, steadily improving project work, and addressing project deviations. Several aspects must be defined when incorporating quality assurance, including the expected level to be reached, qualitative indicators to measure the actual level accomplished per outcome planned, timeframe for assessing quality, management actions, and

roles and responsibilities of project team members. Meeting project criteria assures compliance with strategic goals and standards within the most cost- and resource-efficient manner, enabling chances for expansion and performance improvement. Projects not only foster innovation and strategic planning, but they also have an immediate impact on revenues. Their implementation strengthens the organization's technological skills and creates a foundation for future business success. (Kerzner 2017).

According to (Denger, C., & Olsson, 2005), the ever-increasing complexity and market pressure in engineering projects have necessitated carrying out quality assurance throughout a project to guarantee high quality which is also visible in other sectors. Quality assurance (QA) is an elusive aspect of project management because of the various complex issues related to project management. Conducting quality assurance right from the requirements gathering stage of project development helps in the identification of quality issues right from the requirements engineering phase. Quality assurance from the beginning of a project helps in avoiding instances where project development is based on erroneous initial requirements.

Quality assurance is typically seen as a "lip service," with most documents containing "ticking boxes." Project managers recognize the risk of a project given its novelty, complexity, and purposeful design features, but they do not appear to prioritize the relationship between risk outcomes and the fundamental causes supported by project quality dimensions (Basu 2014).

Therefore, it is against this perspective which has influenced this research as the researcher agrees with Basu, 2014 which is the basis for conducting this research.

1.3 General Objective

To scrutinize the impact of quality assurance on performance of selected faith – based organizations.

1.3.1 Specific objectives

- i. To assess whether inspections influence performance of Caritas Nebbi.
- ii. To estimate if project goals influence performance of Caritas Nebbi.
- iii. To determine if audits influence performance of Caritas Nebbi.
- iv. To measure if risk management influence performance of Caritas Nebbi.

1.4 Research questions

- i. How do inspections influence performance of Caritas Nebbi?
- ii. How do project goals influence performance of Caritas Nebbi?
- iii. How do audits influence performance of Caritas Nebbi?
- iv. How does risk management influence performance of Caritas Nebbi?

Keywords: *Quality, Quality Assurance, performance, faith – based organizations, projects*

2.5 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1 Conceptual Frame work

Independent variables

Dependent variables

Source: Researcher's own impression, 2025

Research Methodology

This section labelled the approaches engaged by the researcher in the study. It expounded the research design, the population under study, sampling techniques and processes, data collection instruments, pilot study, data processing and analysis.

Research Design

The researcher employed descriptive and inferential designs, to scrutinize how quality assurance impacts on performance of faith - based organizations in West Nile sub – region, Uganda.

Target population

Target population of the researcher was on faith - based organizations. The target group were Directors, Program Officers, M&E officers, project accountants, project sponsors and project recipients in Caritas Nebbi. The target population of the study comprised Caritas Nebbi.

Major Findings/ Outcomes

Table 1: Assessment of Quality assurance in CN

	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Inspections are carried out frequently	4.19	.052	.698
The goals of the project being achieved as planned	3.83	.048	.640
Audits are done in the project	2.29	.057	.771
Risk management in the project are carried out by CN.	3.93	.040	.544
Valid N (list wise)	181		

Source: Researcher, 2025

Table 8 shows the assessment of quality assurance in Caritas Nebbi with a high mean of 4.19 indicating a strong agreement that inspections are regularly carried out. The moderate standard deviation (0.698) suggests general agreement among respondents. Inspections enhance quality assurance, helping to track progress and avoiding deviations from the plan in Caritas Nebbi. This can be affirmed by PMBOK guidelines (2021).

The mean of 3.83 suggests agreement that project goals are being achieved. The standard deviation (0.640) indicates a fair level of consistency in responses. Project goal achievement reflects effective planning and quality assurance efforts in place in Caritas Nebbi. (Atkinson et al., 2006), (Besson & Rowe, 2001; Nguyen et al., 2015), (Dekker & Forselius, 2007).

A low mean of 2.29 shows disagreement, suggesting that most respondents believe the project audits are conducted. The relatively higher standard deviation (0.771) indicates some variability in views. Audit is carried out, which supports quality assurance by preventing inadequate quality and unnecessary activities in Caritas Nebbi Chaplowe, (2008).

The mean of 3.93 shows agreement that risks are managed when they occur. The low standard deviation (0.544) shows strong consensus among participants. A responsive and corrective approach is in place, which is crucial for quality assurance and sustaining performance in Caritas Nebbi which concurs with (Denger, C., & Olsson, 2005).

Table 2: Effect of Quality assurance in CN

	Mean		Std. Deviation
	Statistic	Std. Error	Statistic
Inspections have improved performance of the project of CN.	4.25	.048	.651
Project goals being achieved as planned have improved performance of CN.	3.95	.045	.608
Audits have affected performance of the project	2.71	.079	1.057
Risk management have been mitigated by team of CN.	3.94	.049	.656
Valid N (list wise)	181		

Source: Researcher, 2025

A high mean of 4.25 indicates strong agreement that inspections have improved project performance. The relatively low standard deviation (0.651) shows consistent responses among participants. Inspections are key quality assurance practices that significantly enhance project performance in Caritas Nebbi. (Ko et al., 2011; Fanousse et al., 2021)

The mean of 3.95 reflects agreement that achieving planned project goals positively impacts performance. The low standard deviation (0.608) indicates a high level of consensus. Therefore, goal achievement is seen as a strong indicator of performance, supported by effective quality assurance practices in Caritas Nebbi. (Zhu et al., 2020).

The mean of 2.71 indicates disagreement or neutrality, suggesting that audits are carried out to eliminate unplanned activities which are generally perceived to negatively affect performance. The high standard deviation (1.057) indicates a wide range of responses. Audits have eliminated unplanned tasks that potentially would disrupt quality assurance efforts and reduce performance in Caritas Nebbi. (PMI, 2004).

A mean of 3.94 suggests agreement that risk management have enhanced performance. The relatively low standard deviation (0.656) shows consistency in responses in Caritas Nebbi. Responsive problem-solving and error correction strengthen project performance, demonstrating effective quality control mechanisms in Caritas Nebbi. PMBOK guidelines (2021).

4.3.2.3 Correlation between quality Assurance and project performance of CN

Table 3: Correlation between quality Assurance and project performance of CN

Correlations		Inspections have improved performance of the project of CN.	The project goals being achieved as planned have improved performance of CN.	Audits affected performance of the project	Risk management have improved performance of the project by team of CN.
Inspections have improved performance of the project of CN.	Pearson Correlation	1	.285**	-0.022	.332**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.764	.000
	N	181	181	181	181
The project goals being achieved as planned have improved performance of CN.	Pearson Correlation	.285**	1	.220**	.230**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.003	.002
	N	181	181	181	181
Audits have affected performance of the project	Pearson Correlation	-0.022	.220**	1	.137
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.764	.003		.065
	N	181	181	181	181
Risk management have improved performance of the project by team of CN.	Pearson Correlation	.332**	.230**	0.137	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.002	.065	
	N	181	181	181	181

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The correlation table provided above explores the relationship between key elements of project evaluation practices (specifically around inspections, risk management) and their influence on the performance of the CN project. The Pearson correlation coefficients (ranging from -1 to +1) show the strength and direction of relationships between each pair of variables, with statistical significance set at $p < 0.01$. (Zhu et al., 2020)

Inspections and project goals being achieved as planning has a correlation of 0.285** and the significance p value is 0.000 resulting into moderate positive correlation. Effective Inspections in Caritas Nebbi is associated with successful achievement of project goals as well as good oversight which has enhanced organizational performance (Atkinson et al., 2006), (Besson & Rowe, 2001; Nguyen et al., 2015), (Dekker & Forselius, 2007).

Inspections and audits have a correlation of -0.022 and the significance p value is 0.764 which indicates no significant correlation. This suggests that inspections alone do not prevent or predict the impact of audits. In other words, inspections may not be reactive enough to manage surprises in Caritas Nebbi (Tahami, H., & Fakhravar, 2020).

Inspections and risk management have a correlation of 0.332** and a significance p value is 0.000 resulting into a moderate positive correlation. This indicates that when inspections in Caritas Nebbi is frequent, the team is more likely to identify and manage risks effectively, boosting performance of the organization (Denger, C., & Olsson, 2005), PMBOK guidelines (2021).

Planned goals and audits have a correlation of 0.220** and the significance p value is 0.003 indicating a weak-to-moderate positive correlation. This suggests that even when goals at Caritas Nebbi are being met, if audits are not carried out, it can affect performance of the organization indicating tension Chaplowe, (2008).

Planned Goals and risk management have a correlation of 0.230** and the significance p value is 0.002 which is resulting into moderate correlation. Hence, achieving planned goals may require the ability to identify and correct errors, emphasizing the role of flexibility at Caritas Nebbi (Denger, C., & Olsson, 2005). (Zhu et al., 2020).

Audits and risk management have a correlation of 0.137 and the significance p value is 0.065 indicating weak and not statistically significant. Although audits might identify risks, this link isn't strong or clear. Not all surprises in caritas Nebbi result in successful risk management measures (Denger, C., & Olsson, 2005), Chaplowe, (2008).

Summary, Inference and Recommendation

Summary of Key Findings

The research was steered by four main objectives; inspections, project goals, audits and risk management having influence on performance of Caritas Nebbi.

The assessment of quality assurance in Caritas Nebbi analysis suggests that quality assurance practices are actively supporting project performance. Inspections contribute to sustained performance. The achievement of goals and low involvement of risk management further indicate that quality is well-managed. These outcomes reflect a strong quality assurance system that enhances the overall success of the project.

Conclusion

The investigation asserts that quality assurance significantly contributes to improved project performance. Inspections and the risk management are particularly influential, achieving project goals as planned also supports high performance. However, audits show a negative or disruptive effect, highlighting the importance of quality assurance. These outcomes underscore the efficacy of structured quality assurance in driving successful project performance outcomes in Caritas Nebbi.

Recommendations

Strengthening inspection mechanism

Caritas Nebbi should strengthen inspection mechanism where the project managers institutionalize regular and systematic inspections to ensure adherence to quality standards throughout the project lifecycle.

Improving project planning and goal alignment

Improving project planning and goal alignment should be made more realistic where Caritas Nebbi invests in planning, clear goals and continuous monitoring to ensure projects are implemented as planned.

Improve utilization of audit findings

Audit findings should be translated into concrete corrective actions where the management follows up audit recommendations to ensure they contribute performance improvement.

Therefore, demonstrates to be a critical factor for captivating timely corrective actions which in return impact overall project progress.

Institutionalize risk management practices

Caritas Nebbi should adopt comprehensive risk management frameworks, including identification, assessment, mitigation and continuous review.

Staff capacity building

Caritas Nebbi staff should be frequently trained in quality assurance, risk management and performance monitoring to improve effective implementation.

Recommendations for Additional Research

The submissions put forward here are appropriate to the investigation of quality assurance on performance of selected faith – based organizations in Nebbi District, West Nile sub region, Uganda. The varied approaches require studies on exploring why audits have limited direct effect on performance focusing on implementation gaps, comparative studies in other sectors to compare results and enhance generalizability. Furthermore, adopt a longitudinal approach to assess the long term impact of project performance over time. These would offer gaps for further studies in this area.

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